

Bioinformatic assessment of metabolons—what can be predicted?

Sibbe Bakker^{1,2*} Dirk Walther^{2**} Justin van der Hooff^{1***}

¹Wageningen University Bioinformatics Department

²Max Planck Institute of Molecular Plant Physiology

Potsdam

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Abstract

A metabolon is a transient spacial arrangement of enzymes in the same pathway that allows these enzymes to more efficiently catalyse biological reactions. Examples of such metabolons in *Arabidopsis thaliana* include the glycolysis pathway, tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and the purinosome. Currently, laboratory evidence of metabolons comes from protein-protein interaction (PPI) assays, such as fluorophore tagging, and detection of substrate channeling using methods such as the dilution assay. With experimental work, discovering the exact mechanisms of metabolon formation is tedious and expensive, therefore, it is useful to determine how various prediction tools might be applied to this field. To this end, I investigate how each of these three mechanisms can be evaluated with recently-published prediction tools (Combfold, Alpha Fold-3 (AF-3), Seq2phase and PSPhunter). Given the stoichiometry and protein sequences of metabolon subunits, Combfold and AF-3 are able to predict some metabolon complexes with high accuracy (for example, the human mitochondrial tri-functional protein (MTP)). The annotation of liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS) propensity using machine learning methods is fraught with transparency issues regarding sources of training data, which makes results from LLPS models hard to interpret. Prediction of stable metabolon complexes was found to be possible using both AF-3 and or Combfold. Predicting transient complexes still remains a problem. In upcoming work, the Combfold method should be adapted to predict unknown stoichiometry.

*Email: sibbe.bakker@wur.nl. ORCID: 0009-0001-0696-1684

**Internship supervisor from MPIMP-Golm.

***Internship supervisor from WUR.

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Further information: Source of this document can be found on <https://www.overleaf.com/project/660147b971a6f0f154d3de4d>. See Appendix A for additional information such as the location of datasets and code repositories.

Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	Metabolism and metabolons	3
1.2	Known examples of metabolons in plants	4
1.3	Methods to assess metabolons	5
1.4	Current research	6
2	Methodology	7
2.1	Computational infrastructure	7
2.2	Availability of metabolon data	8
2.3	Prediction of metabolon complexes	8
2.3.1	Chosen case studies	8
2.3.2	Generation of structural predictions	8
2.3.3	Analysis and processing of protein structures	9
2.4	Assessment of liquid-liquid phase separation	10
3	Results	11
3.1	Availability of metabolon data	11
3.2	Prediction and analysis of metabolon complexes	12
3.2.1	Comparison to known metabolon structures	12
3.2.2	The predicted glycolysis metabolon	12
3.2.3	The predicted tricarboxylic acid (TCA) metabolon	14
3.2.4	Prediction of ligand protein interactions	15
3.3	Prediction of liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS)	15
4	Discussion	16
4.1	Main findings and relevance	16
4.2	Prediction of metabolon complexes using Combfold	17
4.3	Prediction of liquid-liquid phase separation	18
4.4	Reflection on organisational and academic relevance	19
4.5	Recommendations	20
4.6	Concluding remarks	20
	Appendices	21
A	Availability of code and data	21
B	Statement on the use of AI	21
C	Acknowledgments	21
	References	22

Figure 1: The three modes of metabolic channeling hypothesised by Pareek *et al.* [8]. Direct transfer channeling (a) works via a molecular tunnel that constrains the metabolites to go to a single active site. In the various types of proximity channeling, the metabolites are constrained in movement to stay near the enzymatic chain. Via indirect interactions such as electrostatic effects or a molecular cage (b). In cluster channeling (c), enzymes and metabolites stay in the same micro-compartment formed by LLPS. Figures reprinted from Pareek *et al.* [8].

1 Introduction

1.1 Metabolism and metabolons

The metabolism of an organism represents the set of chemical reactions required to sustain it [1]. Such reactions are catalysed by enzymes. Enzymes are proteins that have a specific binding site and reactivity to speed up the conversion between specific substrates [2]. Enzymes and the substrates they convert form enzymatic pathways, where one enzymatic conversion of a substrate can lead to the next one. Three examples of well characterised metabolic pathways are the glycolysis catabolic pathway, which mediates the breakdown of sugars into pyruvate [3]; the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle, responsible for the breakdown of pyruvate and the subsequent release of energy [4, 5]; or the *de novo* purin biosynthesis (DPBS) pathway which manages the production of DNA required for growth [6].

Metabolism is known to have a spacial organisation that is vital for controlling enzymatic flux [7]. Some sequential metabolic processes can temporarily be arranged close together, and process the substrate within the same environment—a structure called a metabolon. In such a metabolon, the substrate for one enzyme is provided by its neighbour in a process called metabolic channeling (Figure 1). This makes the metabolites less likely to leak out of the metabolic pathway. Depending on the mechanism of spacial arrangement of the enzymes involved, there can be three ways a metabolite can be channeled: 1) Direct transfer channeling, when there is a tunnel between two subsequent enzymes through which the metabolite is transferred (Figure 1a); 2) Proximity channeling, there is a chemical/or steric mechanisms—such as electrostatic forces (Figure 1b) or a pocket (Figure 1b)—that keeps the metabolites within the metabolon; 3) Cluster channeling, where chemical properties of the enzymes in subsequent steps cause them to be sequester via liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS) (Figure 1c).

Direct channeling and proximity channeling happens via protein-protein interactions

within a protein complex. For example, if the two enzymes come together in a way that makes their reaction centres closer, or better connected, the metabolite can be transferred between the two enzymes with reduced leakage. LLPS happens with proteins that have a high degree of interacting domains and a high degree of disorder [9]. Under specific environmental conditions, such as a pH or salt concentration, the proteins can be driven into a liquid phase with a different composition than the surrounding environment, forming a LLPS cluster (Figure 1c).

Besides making the overall reaction more efficient by increasing catalytic activity, a metabolon can sequester metabolites and decrease toxic effects of intermediate reaction products. Because of the reduced leakage of reaction products, a metabolon may serve as an efficient way to control metabolic flux at a branch point in a metabolic pathway. Metabolons are shown to regulate enzymatic activities in a wide range of organisms, from human [10], to bacteria, fungi and plants.

1.2 Known examples of metabolons in plants

For a multi-enzyme complex to be called a metabolon, there must be evidence of substrate channeling. While many metabolons are speculated to exist in plants, only four have been experimentally shown: the glycolysis, TCA, phenylpropanoid pathway, and dhurrin synthesis [11]. In this report, the focus will be on the metabolons of glycolysis, TCA cycle and the DPBS pathway. In human cell lines, DPBS enzymes are not lipid encapsulated and easily exchange with the cytosol, indicating that the formation of the purinosome likely driven by LLPS [6]. Of the plant metabolons that are experimentally described, not much is known about the structure of the complex. Here I discuss the glycolysis and TCA metabolons, which are important for the degradation of sugars in mammals and plants [12].

A good example of a direct-channeled metabolon in plants is the glycolysis complex [16, 17] of *A. thaliana*. This metabolon consist of the three following homodimers: phosphoglycerate mutase (PGAM), enolase and pyruvate kinase (PYK4). Besides the conversion of 3-phosphoglycerate to pyruvate, it is also known to mediate the co-localisation of the mitochondrion with the chloroplast [16]. This is evident from the PGAM or enolase knockouts that show a reduced association between the mitochondrion and chloroplast. It is known that the glycolysis metabolon binds to membrane transporters of the chloroplast and the mitochondrion [16]. How the association of this metabolon happens is unclear. Two possible mechanisms of this association are interaction with actin filaments, or that the metabolon itself forms a filament-like structure.¹

The TCA metabolon is known to be channeled indirectly, via electrostatic forces [14, 18]. The TCA metabolon consist of the malate dehydrogenase (MDH)-citrate synthase (CSY)-aconitase (ACO) enzymes [14, 18]. In the TCA cycle, pyruvate from glycolysis is oxidised and converted to down stream metabolites that are used in amino acid synthesis or the production of fatty acids [5].

In human cell lines, the purinosome is an example of LLPS mediated channeling [19, 20]. The purinosome is responsible for the *de novo* formation of nucleotides via *de novo* purin biosynthesis (DPBS). The DPBS pathway starts with 5-phosphoribosyl-1-pyrophosphate (PRPP), derived from the pentose phosphate pathway [6]. The human

¹Alistar Fernie, personal communication.

Figure 2: Examples of metabolon structures that are resolved in mammalian primary metabolism. a) Shows a direct substrate channel in the human mitochondrial trifunctional protein (MTP) as described by Xia *et al.* [13]. b) Shows an electrostatic channel on the surface of the TCA metabolon introduced by Bulutoglu *et al.* [14] using site directed mutagenesis. c) Shows a diagramme of the human purinosome with the trifunctional glycinamide ribonucleotidetransferase (GART) complex that associates with PRPP amidotransferase (PPAT), formylglycinamide ribonucleotide synthase (FGAMS), which in turn interact with aminoimidazole carboxamide ribonucleotide transformylase (ATIC) and adenylosuccinate lyase (ASL) and succinylaminoimidazole carboxamide ribonucleotide synthetase (PAICS).

purinosome is composed of the trifunctional glycinamide ribonucleotidetransferase (GART) complex that associates with PRPP amidotransferase (PPAT), formylglycinamide ribonucleotide synthase (FGAMS), which in turn interact with aminoimidazole carboxamide ribonucleotide transformylase (ATIC) and adenylosuccinate lyase (ASL) and succinylaminoimidazole carboxamide ribonucleotide synthetase (PAICS) [14].

Understanding the structural mechanisms of metabolons is crucial for obtaining a deeper understanding into plant metabolism, as besides the primary metabolism described above, metabolons are also expected to play a large role in secondary metabolism [21].

1.3 Methods to assess metabolons

Two types of evidence are needed to confirm if a metabolic reaction takes place in a metabolon: evidence of protein-protein interaction (PPI) and evidence of channeling [22]. PPIs are experimentally assessed using techniques such as fluorescent labeling, mass spectrometry-proximity tagging or yeast2hybrid assays. These experimentally verified PPIs are kept track of in databases such as string-db [23] or the Complex portal [24]. Evidence of channeling is obtained through *in vitro* assays, such as dilution experiments or transient-time analysis [25]. In dilution experiments, an isotopically labeled substrate is added to an ongoing reaction, after which the reaction is stopped. By determining how much of the labeled substrate is converted, channeling can be assessed. The greater the channeling efficiency of the metabolon, the lesser the amount of labeled substrate that is converted in the reaction [25]. Currently there is no database

where results from channeling experiments can be deposited.

When both a channeling action and PPI are found, attempts can be made to elucidate the structure of the metabolon. This can be done using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and X ray crystallography. These structures are deposited in protein structure databases such as Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics (RCSB) protein data bank (PDB) (RCSB-PDB). This is an expensive experiment, that often has a lot of practical barriers (for example, a complex could be too unstable to crystallise). In these situations, recent innovations in deep learning based structure prediction, such as Alpha Fold-2 (AF-2) [26], have shown their use: Launay *et al.* [27] were able produce a biologically useful model of the ubiquinone metabolon in *Escherichia coli*. More recent modeling techniques based on generative neural networks, such as Alpha Fold-3 (AF-3) [28] and Rozetta Fold All Atom (RFAA) [29] have not yet seen published use for the prediction of metabolons.

When the channeling of the metabolon instead suspected to be mediated via LLPS the LLPS can be investigated by imaging or fluorescent tagging [30]. By attaching a fluorophore to a suspected LLPS protein LLPS droplets can be visualised *in vivo* [31]. Movement of protein between the main phase in the cytosol and the LLPS droplets can be measured by bleaching the fluorophores of the LLPS droplets with intense light, and measuring the duration of fluoresce recovery in the droplet.

1.4 Current research

Structures of metabolons are difficult to obtain. Assessing the possibility of metabolon prediction using the aforementioned deep-learning methods would allow experimentalist to obtain hypothesised structures to get ideas on the metabolon mechanism, before the release of experimental structures. This is important, as investigating crystal structures of metabolons is challenging, since the complexes are rarely stable. Currently, AF-2 based modeling and mechanistic docking techniques have been used to obtain predictions of metabolon complexes [27]. These methods are complicated to use for people which little experience in bioinformatics. Additionally, recent innovations in generative neural networks have made it possible to predict interactions between general bio-molecules such as substrates, nucleotides and proteins.

In this internship, I set out determine whether, using recently released deep learning models, it is possible to predict a metabolon *in silico* using information from sequences and literature evidence. Each of the three proposed mechanism of metabolon channeling (Figure 1) will be taken into account by designing two pipelines, one for structurally mediated metabolon: direct channeled and proximity, and one for cluster channeled metabolons (Figure 3). The input for the predictions will be protein sequence data and known stoichiometry from from Uniprot and literature information on specific metabolons. Since current structural prediction methods are only accessible for more experienced bioinformatician, reproducibility and documentation of the final pipeline will be a main priority.

I start out by assessing what data is available on metabolons from the literature and public databases. This I will do by compiling data from various resources into a central dataset with a knowledge graph approach. For the structure prediction of structurally mediated metabolons, the direct channeled glycolysis metabolon of *A. thaliana* will be assessed. This will be done by predicting the metabolon by assuming that it is a

Figure 3: Overview of the internship project. In this internship, methods for predicting *A. thaliana* metabolons *in silico* are assessed, with the the glycolysis and TCA metabolon being used as case-studies. Made using biorender.

stable complex, and determining whether the predicted structure matches the current understanding of it. As an aside, a brief assessment of ligand-protein interaction is included—since ligands can affect protein complex confirmation. In the assessment of the predicted structures it is not always possible to compare against known experimental structures. In these cases, the known PPI interfaces of the complex will be used with to judge the prediction. For the LLPS mediated interactions, a gene ontology (GO) term enrichment analysis will used to determine whether the function of proteins that undergo LLPS have any relation to metabolic functions.

2 Methodology

2.1 Computational infrastructure

To make documentation and reproducibility easier, the Snakemake workflow language by Köster and Rahmann [32] was used as the basis for all pipelines. The Max Planck Institute (MPI)-Golm servers were used for designing and composing all Snakemake pipeline designs. All pipelines used a common workflow template (Appendix A). Pipelines were run on the Raven cluster of the MPI using the Snakemake Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management (SLURM) executor plugin [33]. Dependencies and environments were handled with Pixi [34], which made it possible to transfer a workflow to different computational setups automatically. Within Snakemake, the environment requirements for each rule were specified as a Conda [35] environment. As a shell environment, the data-centric Nu shell [36], was chosen. To handle resource description framework (RDF) datasets, the Oxigraph graph-database by Pellissier Tanon [37] was chosen for its portability.

2.2 Availability of metabolon data

To get a first hand assessment of the usability of structural prediction models such as AF-2 an earlier whole proteome PPI prediction of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* made by Humphreys *et al.* [38] was used. To construct this dataset, the authors built multiple sequence alignments (MSAs) for each protein isoform pair in *S. cerevisiae* using Orthofinder. The PPIs, available as an edge list, were assessed for presence of previously reported *S. cerevisiae* metabolons, as listed in the previous section (subsection 2.2). The dataset was interrogated using R using Tidyverse [39] and IGraph [40, 41] to find multi-enzyme complexes that contained members from the same Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway annotation.

Using the full text search keyword ‘metabolon’ RCSB database was searched for known protein structures of metabolons with the aim of using them as the ground truth for assessment of predictions. Further searches for metabolon structures were made on Google Scholar with the search term ‘metabolon structure’.

2.3 Prediction of metabolon complexes

2.3.1 Chosen case studies

As covered in the Introduction, the glycolysis and TCA metabolon of *A. thaliana* are known to assemble into a metabolon that is channeled via the structure of the protein complex. The canonical protein sequences from Uniprot were used as input for the generation of structural predictions. In cases where the stoichiometry was unknown, it was taken to be 1:1.

2.3.2 Generation of structural predictions

To predict the structure of metabolons such as the glycolysis and TCA metabolon, the interactions that form the metabolon complex are to be predicted. Recently, two new methods for predicting the structure of protein complexes were published: AF-3 [28] and Combfold [42]. The AF-3 method works via a generative neural network, whereas Combfold is a combinatorial graph algorithm that finds the most likely complex out of a set of possible combinations of subunits.

The input to the Combfold algorithm is the set of all possible subunit structures that make up the whole complex, produced by Alpha Fold-2 Multimer (AF2M). To arrive at a prediction of the overall protein complex, two representative subunits of an AF2M predicted interaction are aligned to each other so that the root mean square superposition residual (RMSD) between them is minimised. This has the effect of making the representative (or highest) quality AF2M predictions fit in the complex of the two subunits. This process can be repeated iteratively to combine interacting combinations of subunits. For each output structure, Combfold produces a weighted score that is based on the score of the subunit transformation and the importance of the transformation. The transformation score is a scaled version of the position aligned error (PAE) metric, produced by AF2M. The transformation importance is the number of amino acids that are moved by the transformation.

In this report, subunit pairs were predicted using AF2M via the Colabfold toolkit [43] (v1.5.5), which offers a user-friendly interface to the protein folding predictors released

by DeepMind. Wherever possible, tri-mers were also predicted using AF2M and used as Combfold input, as the authors of Combfold found this to help in the assembly of challenging complexes. To produce the MSA alignments for AF2M input, the Mmseq database [44] was used with default settings. For each subunit combination, five structures were predicted with 20 recycles each. The above methodology was written up into a Snakemake pipeline and version 'complex-prediction' v0.3.0 was used in the analysis and is available on GitHub (Appendix A).

Because protein-ligand interaction is known to affect the structure of the overall protein complex, the NeuralPlexer (NP) tool was assessed. Like AF-3, NP is also a generative neural network: NP takes sequences, ligand molecules, and optionally structures as input [45]. AF-3 is able to take additional information from MSA to determine which regions of the protein are more conserved. Both AF-3 and AF2M models produce predicted TM (pTM), interface pTM (ipTM), predicted LDDT (pLDDT) and PAE metrics. The pTM score represents the predicted template modeling (TM) score (0 for no similarity, 1 for perfect match, and values below 0.3 indicating a match between random structures [46]), and is an overall metric of how confident the model is. The ipTM score, is the same as the pTM, but only considers the subunits that are part of a PPI interface.

2.3.3 Analysis and processing of protein structures

The predicted metabolon complexes were visually assessed with Pymol [47]. The Pymol show_bumps module [48] was used to visualise steric clashes. The cif2pdb script written by Spencer Bliven [49] was used to convert mmCIF files to PDB files. In situations where molecular coordinates of ligands were stored as SDF files, they were loaded into a single PDB file using RDkit [50] and the biopython PDB module [51]. The BiopPthon SeqIO module was used to convert the chain records of a PDB file to a fasta file, where the sequence of each subunit is a record.

For comparisons between two protein complexes, the USalign [52] program was used to calculate the TM score. To make it easier to assess the structure of the predicted complex, protein contact maps and subunit graphs were produced from each complex. Protein contact maps show which parts between two amino acid sequences are physically close to each other [53]. Contacts between the subunits were investigated by counting the number of pairwise distances between the C_{α} atoms between subunits that were less than 15Å using the PDB module of the BioPython package [51]. The residues within 15Å of each other were considered to interact. The number of contacting residues was used as an edge weight metric in a Networkx [54] object for the subunit interaction graph. The resulting subunit interaction graph was plotted with Matplotlib, where the thickness of the edge between two nodes indicates the amount of C_{α} atoms that were considered to interact. To find protein-ligand binding sites, the protein ligand interaction profiler (Plip, [55]) was used with PDB files as input.

For all other Python-based analysis, tabular data was handled using Polars and plots were drawn using Matplotlib and seaborn. Using the PDB module of the Biopython library, further summary statistics for each complex were compiled regarding the total number of steric clashes content of the β -factor column of the PDB file. Clashes were counted according to Kenyon [56], where the distance between atoms is compared to their atomic radii, if their distance is smaller than the sum $\times 0.63$ of their radii. Disulphite bridges and peptide bonds were ignored. Using the Shrake-

Table 1: The LLPS prediction methods assessed during this internship. These LLPS detection tools were trained on protein sequences that included signal peptides.

Programme	Description	Citation
PSPire*	This model takes into account the structure of the protein.	Hou <i>et al.</i> [63]
PSPhunter	Calculates a single LLPS propensity score based on the 'sticker-spacer' model [64]. Trained on human known LLPS data. The dataset of negative cases is not clear.	Sun <i>et al.</i> [65]
Seq2Phase	Calculates scores based on the 'client-scaffold' model [66]. Trained on human and yeast LLPS data.	Miyata and Iwasaki [67]

* Could not be not ran locally. † programs for which no source code is available.

Ruply algorithm [57] implemented by the mdtraj package [58], the per-residue solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) score was calculated. Using a Python script adapted from Kannan [59], the dihedral angles were extracted per residue of the PDB file and plotted.

When possible, existing structures of the RCSB-PDB were used to verify the validity of CombFold predictions. This 'combifold-benchmark' version v0.1.0 benchmark pipeline is used in the report and available on GitHub (Appendix A).

2.4 Assessment of liquid-liquid phase separation

Various machine learning models have been recently developed to address the problem of predicting which proteins are capable of LLPS (Table 1). These tools use different definitions of LLPS and were trained with different datasets. To test the performance of the recently published prediction metrics two datasets were obtained with the aim of producing a single evaluation dataset. The first evaluation dataset was constructed by combining LLPS annotations from the DrLLPS database into a single dataset [60]. The annotations from the databases were written to RDF the Uniprot schema. Because the DrLLPS database does not document proteins not classified as LLPS, a second dataset also assessed that did include negative cases. The resulting graph database was queried for database annotations for the Baker's yeast proteome and the LLPS predictions from each tool. This data was loaded into R, and the area under the curve (AUC) curves were drawn for each predictor using the ROCit package [61]. The Youden index, the predictor threshold at which sensitivity and specificity are both maximised, was also calculated using ROCit. These values were plotted on a ridge plot of the density of predictor scores made using GGridges [62].

For the definitions of the classification, the scaffold and client class defined by DrLLPS were both considered phase separating. For the evaluation, LLPS without intrinsic disorder (noID-PSP) and the LLPS proteins with intrinsic disorder (ID-PSP) used to train PSP-ire were both considered to be phase separating.

3 Results

3.1 Availability of metabolon data

Existing predicted PPI, such as the prediction of complexes of *S. cerevisiae* by Humphreys *et al.* [38], it is clear that predicting metabolons at a proteome scale is not feasible. The dataset Humphreys *et al.* [38] does describe known subunit interactions in the primary metabolism of *S. cerevisiae* (Figure 4). Any interactions between enzymes of the primary metabolism within metabolons, such as the glycolytic metabolon reported by Araiza-Olivera *et al.* [68] to consist of glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH), phosphoglycerate kinase (PGK) and aldolase (ALD) is not predicted by Humphreys *et al.* [38]. This indicates that other protein complex prediction methods are needed.

Figure 4: Protein interactions predicted by Humphreys *et al.* [38] in *S. cerevisiae* which have members that are annotated with the KEGG term ‘primary metabolism’. Nodes are unique proteins, edges represent predicted PPIs between the proteins.

Experimental data on metabolon structures is rare: in the the RCSB-PDB one structure is tagged as ‘metabolon’: [PDB: 6DV2] [69]. This hetero-quatromer found in human mitochondria, published by Xia *et al.* [13] is responsible for the β -oxidation of fatty acids. Which allows the body to use fat as an energy source [70]. Bulutoglu *et al.* [14] describes the structure of a TCA metabolon, obtained via classical docking studies using previously resolved crystals of the subunits. Further predictions include Launay *et al.* [27] who used AF-2 to predict a ubiquitinone metabolon of *E. coli*. Also Skalidis *et al.* [71] managed to recover the structure of a succinyl-CoA producing metabolon that participates in the TCA cycle of *Chaetomium thermophilum* using a combination of AF2M, microscopy and classical *in silico* docking ([PDB: 8oiu]).

3.2 Prediction and analysis of metabolon complexes

3.2.1 Comparison to known metabolon structures

In RCSB-PDB, the only metabolon that is structurally resolved is the human mitochondrial tri-functional protein (MTP) [PDB: 6DV2]. This complex is predicted well by both AF-3 and Combfold, with the TM score being 0.99 and 0.97, respectively (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Prediction of the human MTP. The crystal structure is red (resolution=3.6Å, [PDB: 6DV2]) and the prediction is blue.

3.2.2 The predicted glycolysis metabolon

To determine the differences between the glycolysis metabolon predicted using Combfold to that of AF-3, protein contact maps were constructed. Two residues are considered in contact if their C_{α} atoms were within a radius of 15Å of each other. These contact maps show that the PGAM-enolase-PYK4 interface hypothesised by Zhang *et al.* [16] is not recovered by AF-3 (Figure 6). The interaction of the enolase homodimers is predicted in a similar way between Combfold (Figure 7d) and AF-3 (Figure 6c). The TM score for these predicted *A. thaliana* enolase dimers vs the known human enolase dimer is 0.95 for AF2M and 0.96 for AF-3. From the subunit interaction graphs, it is clear that AF-3 predicts different complexes than Combfold.

The biological hypothesis of interaction between the members of the glycolysis metabolon is that the PGAM dimer interacts with the enolase dimer and the enolase

(a) Predicted structure. The enolase dimer is yellow and purple. the PGAM dimer is blue and green, the PYK4 dimer is white and pink.

(b) Subunit interaction graph of the predicted glycolysis metabolon.

(c) Contact map of the enolase dimer.

Figure 6: AF-3 prediction of the glycolysis metabolon. The model has a ipTM = 0.32 and pTM = 0.42. Seed = 1.

(a) Predicted structure. The enolase dimer is yellow and purple. the PGAM dimer is blue and green, the PYK4 dimer is white and pink.

(b) Steric clashes (red) between the PGAM and Enolase dimer.

(c) Subunit interaction graph of the predicted glycolysis metabolon

(d) Contact map of the enolase dimer.

Figure 7: Combifold prediction of the glycolysis metabolon. Combifold Score = 91.07.

dimer interacts with the PYK4 dimer. The ordering of the complexes predicted by AF-3 (Figure 6b) does not match this hypothesis, as AF-3 did not find that enolase interacts with PYK4. AF-3 placed PGAM in the centre of the complex instead of at the start of the complex. The ordering of the Combifold prediction (Figure 7c) is more close to the hypothesised ordering, the only expected aspect of the ordering is that it predicts PYK4 to interact with PGAM.

Inspecting the Combifold prediction with Pymol reveals that the interaction surface for the subunits of the glycolysis metabolon has a high number of steric clashes (Figure 7b) this indicates that an additional relaxation step is needed.

3.2.3 The predicted TCA metabolon

The TCA cycle metabolon in its entirety could only be predicted using Combifold, as its size exceeded the token limit (5000) set by AF-3. Even then, the ACO2M enzyme had to be split up in its functional domains because it exceeded the token limit of AF2M. The predicted complex is a filamentous complex (Figure 8a) with a Combifold

(a) Ray trace of the predicted TCA metabolon. (b) Subunit interaction graph of the predicted TCA metabolon.

Figure 8: Combifold prediction of the TCA metabolon. Combifold score = 86.73.

score of 86.72.

The hypothesised ordering of the TCA metabolon is MDHM-CISY-ACO. This ordering was not predicted by Combifold, instead, one part of the ACO complex (the Aconitase C domain of ACO2M and ACO3M) were predicted to interact with MDH2 and MDH1. Furthermore, this predicted fibre-like MDHM-CISY-ACO complex is not observed in mechanistic protein docking studies such as Bulutoglu *et al.* [14].

3.2.4 Prediction of ligand protein interactions

Since metabolons are complexes that form and disassemble in response to concentrations of specific metabolites. It is important to consider the possible conformations in the presence of ligand. One tool that has been developed for this is NP [45]. To assess the usefulness of NP within the Combifold workflow, the structure of the enolase dimer with its substrate 2-Phosphoglyceric acid (2PG) is predicted. If this prediction is realistic, then NP can be used as a replacement of AF2M. The enolase dimer of *A. thaliana* predicted using NP is unrealistic. The two subunits of the homodimer overlap each other almost completely along the main chain (Figure 9) since the diagonal of the contact map of the two subunits is fully filled in. The TM score of the alignment to human enolase [PDB: 5TD9] indicates that the NP prediction is not related to the resolved crystal structure.

Further structure prediction attempts with NP were not successful, the model predicts the ligand in unrealistic locations and predicts that the protein is full of cavities. Also other protein-ligand interactions such as NATA1, a putrescine acetyltransferase important for plant defence [72], could not be reproduced.

3.3 Prediction of LLPS

Before the possibility of phase separation of the purinisome can be assessed, reliable LLPS annotation tools are needed. For an overview of the performance of the recently published LLPS classifiers, a comparison to the training data of PSPire is assessed. A comparison of the LLPS predictors against the same dataset reveals that some predictors have problems with their fit. Using the testing dataset from PSPire as the

(a) The enolase homodimer with 2 molecules of 2PG. (b) Contact map of the homodimer.

Figure 9: The NP prediction for enolase. TM score comparison to the human enolase complex ([PDB: 5TD9]) is 0.36.

classification, shows that the PSPire predictor ($AUC = 1$, Figure 10a) is a ‘perfect’ classifier. This, of course, is unrealistic and indicates that the PSPire classifier may be over fit. In the publication of PSPire Hou *et al.* [63], the authors report a more realistic AUC, between 0.86 and 0.84.

Because of the annotation quality of the training data for Seq2Phase and PSPhunter, these classifiers are not easily interpretable, therefore it is my assessment that quality predictions of LLPS are not possible at the time, at least with the models investigated in this internship (Table 1).

4 Discussion

4.1 Main findings and relevance

Metabolons, temporary arrangements of enzymes that together catalyse the steps for a metabolic reaction play an important role in metabolism of plants [73]. A better understanding of these channeled enzyme-enzyme complexes could lead the way to better engineered plant metabolisms [74]. In this work, I assessed the use of machine learning methods to resolve metabolon structures for two types of metabolons, those that form a (temporary) protein complex and those that associate in LLPS. I found that, even with the recent improvements in deep learning architectures there are still barriers to quick and accurate protein structure and LLPS predictions. For the prediction tools of protein structure, the biggest issue is not their lack of accuracy, but their lack of reproducible environments and quality documentation. The LLPS prediction tools too show this, have the added problem of opaque training and testing data, since the source of a label is not documented. Despite these barriers, approaches such as CombFold clearly show their use: they are able to infer some metabolon complexes (such as the human MTP) with high accuracy. Other structures, such as the glycolysis, or TCA metabolon are predicted with less regard to biology—showing that careful interpretation is needed.

(a) Receiver-operator curves for the different LLPS predictors. (b) Distribution of LLPS predictor scores.

Figure 10: Performance of the recently published LLPS models on the testing dataset for the Human proteome curated by Hou *et al.* [63] for the development of PSPire.

A previous work that used deep learning methods to assess possible metabolon structures was Launay *et al.* [27]. They produced a curated set of MSAs as input for AF2M and AF-2. In this work, MSAs were obtained via Colabfold from the Mmseqs database as per Shor and Schneidman-Duhovny [42]. This represent one avenue of improvement for situations where the Mmseqs database is not able to supply high quality MSAs. Russell *et al.* [75], used molecular dynamics (MD) simulation to model the glycolytic metabolon. In upcoming work, it would be useful to see how Combfold holds up against these results.

4.2 Prediction of metabolon complexes using Combfold

The complex prediction pipeline assessed in this internship is able to predict the structure of some protein complexes. Before these structures can be used in downstream analysis the steric clashes should be resolved in a assisted Model Building and Energy Refinement (AMBER) [76] relaxation step. This step can be implemented via the AF2M application programming interface (API). After this step, the model can be assessed with tools that can find direct channels, such as CAVERdock [77]. The APBS suite [78] can be used to assess the possibility of a surface channel mediated electrostatics.

After these channels have been found, MD analysis can be used to assess their functionality. The protein structures made using Combfold and AF-3 can be of high accuracy to use for this purpose, as done in work such as [75].

In some cases, the output of Combfold can be more usable than the output of AF-3: AF-3 is known to have decreased accuracy for larger structures; the licence of AF-3 does not allow users to analyse the produced structures with automated protein-ligand docking tools. Combfold does not place any usage restrictions on its output, but is more computationally intense, as for each n amount of unique protein chains, $((n + 1)n)/2$ possible protein interactions need to be investigated using AF2M. For example, for the

human MTP prediction, about half a gigabyte of intermediate files (PDBs, MSAs etc) were produced. This amount increases rapidly as the complexity of the protein complex increases (16GB of intermediate files are produced for a hetero-8-mer complex). This means that large scale usage of the Combifold method is only tenable on a cluster setup. With the pipeline produced in this report, it is the hope that the bar of accessibility gets lowered to just knowing the basics of Snakemake. Regardless of the chosen method, there are two fundamental difficulties in predicting protein complexes: instability of protein complexes and predicting complexes with unknown stoichiometry. For these problems, protein complex prediction methods like Combifold could be more effective than using a single model such as AF-3, since methods that assemble a protein complex from combinations of possible complexes can sample more varied structures.

Sadly, due to issues with computational reproducibility, it was not possible to use NP to predict protein pairs with a ligand. While it was possible for the provided Docker image to be used, I did not succeed in predicting protein-ligand structures with high accuracy. The documentation and support for NP is minimal, and not sufficient for new users to understand how NP can be used in prediction tasks. These problems aforementioned issues were raised in a Github issue that now—after 1 month—still does not have a response. One promising machine learning framework that could not be assessed in the four month duration of this internship was the RFAA model. This is an open-source alternative to AF-3. There has not been a clean up of its code or dependency structure, so installing RFAA was outside of the scope of this report. In the future, RFAA and tools like it should be shared in a more reproducible manner such as a conda-forge package or a Docker image. The open-source Colabfold project managed to encapsulate the AF-2 model into a well structured Python project. A similar thing may be done for RFAA. This would make protein folding models more easily accessible, making it more easy for predictions to reach experimentalist.

Regarding the issues with the TCA and glycolysis prediction, it could be, that the TCA and glycolysis metabolon are more unstable than the membrane-embedded human MTP. With the current pipeline, accurately judging predicted PPI-contacts is challenging as the contact maps used during this research are only an approximation that may give unspecific information. This is because defining a ‘contact’ as two C_{α} atoms that are within 15Å of each other does not capture specific interactions, a lower threshold, such as 8Å recommended by Di Paola *et al.* [79] could have been more informative. In a next iteration, an actual contact map could also be calculated with tools such as [80].

4.3 Prediction of liquid-liquid phase separation

Beside the formation of (transient) protein complexes, it is also possible for metabolons to form by associating in a LLPS. Such associations are hard to study *in vivo* so data availability is quite limited. The machine learning algorithms for the prediction of LLPS assessed in this work (Seq2Phase and PSPHunter) have a similar architecture: an embedding step followed by an ensemble binary classifier. The ability of proteins to undergo LLPS is determined in part by sequence of their sequence such as intrinsic disorder and hydrophobicity [9, 81]. A protein is considered intrinsically disordered if it does not possess a single stable tertiary structure, but instead changes between many different forms [82]. Therefore, one can expect machine learning algorithms to

extract usefully information. However, LLPS is also driven in large part by cellular conditions, such as protein concentration, temperature and pH [9]. This information is not encoded in the protein sequence and this therefore represents a inherent source of inaccuracy.

An additional issue with the models assessed in this report, is that the LLPS prediction models are difficult to interpret. This is because the labels of the training data come from different database sources which have different quality standards and label definitions. For example, the Seq2phase model constructs its negative set (the non LLPS proteins) based on Cluster Database at High Identity with Tolerance (CD-hit, Li and Godzik [83]) clustering where protein sequence clusters that did not contain DrLLPS records were assigned as ‘non-LLPS’. The PSPhunter model was trained using ‘various sources including PhaseSepDB, LLPSDB, DrLLPS and PhaSePro’ All of these databases have different methods for annotation and quality standards for their records. The authors of PSPhunter do not indicate which part of their training/testing data came from which source. To obtain ‘non-LLPS’ annotations, the authors of the PSPhunter model take Uniprot proteomes there there are at least 10 instances of LLPS annotations. Then the authors selected all proteins with a single domain that were not annotated as undergoing LLPS. These training data sets are quite different and make no guaranties about the accuracy of the labels: as the negative training and testing data can contain proteins that can undergo LLPS, but for which this behaviour is not yet described.

If there is a future need for a machine-learning model that can understand LLPS, a well annotated dataset is paramount. Recently, such a system was developed by Aspromonte *et al.* [84]. With both the source of the annotation, as well as the identity of the reviewer being recorded, quality of data from Disprot is easily verified. The evaluation of the models using the training data of PSPire is not optimal, given that the source training and data of PSPire is not easy to interpret. As a follow up, the receiver operator curve (ROC) curve should be re-assessed using the content of the Disprot database, to get a better estimate under which conditions the LLPS predictors are accurate.

Like the machine learning models for protein structure prediction, the LLPS models also suffered from this issue. While the seq2phase model was straight-forward to install, the PSPhunter program required bug-fixing Perl scripts before it could be used. The PhasePhred program did not have its source code published. In this report, the PSPhunter and seq2phase programs were placed into a reproducible pipeline for LLPS prediction. Even when the installation issues are resolved, the seq2phase and PSPhunter both have issues with longer protein sequences, but do not report this limitation in their documentation or error messages.

4.4 Reflection on organisational and academic relevance

Even though no new insights on metabolon structures were gained during this internship, a method was developed for the AG-Walther group to use Combfold to predict protein-protein complexes. The main Combfold pipeline is reproducible and configured to work on the SLURM batch system of the MPI cluster. In combination with the pipeline for analysing the correctness of protein predictions, the researcher who takes over from me will have an easier time starting out with predictions of protein complexes. Already,

researchers from other project have used the program for the distance map and the Snakemake pipeline for Combfold. The finding that the current machine learning based LLPS annotation are not easy to interpret is useful for the AG-Walther, as the group has collaborators that work with biological mechanism related to LLPS: such as the cold response in *A. thaliana*. Now, we know it does not make sense to recommend the usage of algorithm such as Seq2phase, PSPhunter and PSPire—until there is more understanding of the sources of their training data.

This internship significantly added to my technical ability, now I have experience with batch systems such as SLURM, and how they fit into workflow languages like Snakemake. I managed to transfer this knowledge to the department in a seminar where I gave an introduction to Snakemake. While I did use such workflow systems before during my study at Wageningen university and research (WUR), I never used them with the more complex functionality (modules, checkpoints) that they offer the user. In upcoming bioinformatic projects that I take on, I will be able to more easily estimate what it will take to deliver a reproducible analysis. At WUR, I took an introductory course for structural biology, which are well complemented by the practical experience I obtained at AG-Walther. Now I am better informed on the current state of the field, and aware of how to implement the analysis of protein structures.

4.5 Recommendations

Due to the high computational complexity, the *ab initio* prediction of metabolons from protein data is not possible with the Combfold approach described here. However, Combfold presents a method to assess the possible structure of of metabolons in situations where the members of the interaction are known, but there is not available crystal structure. The most two important improvements to this described Combfold method are to allow for an unknown stoichiometry of interaction partners, and to find a way take into account that complexes may be temporary.

4.6 Concluding remarks

In this internship, machine learning based prediction methods for assessing the structure of metabolons was assessed. Methods for predicting protein-protein complexes are well developed but do not work on all structures. Avenues for improvement are to stochastic into account, by adapting the Combfold algorithm to sample different possible conformations of a complex. Methods for predicting LLPS of a protein sequence are less developed because the precedence of the test and training data is not well documented.

To continue, more structured data is needed, both to make new predictions (what proteins form which complex, what are the channeled metabolites?) and to validated the prediction algorithm (with what accuracy can known structures of metabolons be predicted?). For this curated databases on protein interactions such as the Complex portal [24] and databases on LLPS such as Disprot [84] are important to compare predicted metabolon structures to data from literature. When the above improvements have been made, the complex-prediction pipeline can be used address open questions in plant metabolon structure. One open question is to determine the structure of the *A. thaliana* glycolytic complex, since it is not known how this PGAM-enolase-PYK4 metabolon binds to the chloroplast and mitochondria.

Appendices

A Availability of code and data

Overview of datasets and public repositories The datasets produced during my period at the Max Planck Institute for plant physiology (MPIMP) and the documentation and code that belongs to it. It includes links to Snakemake pipelines, such as the Combifold pipeline, or the analyses of protein structures from methods subsection 2.3.3.

See—[10.5281/zenodo.11942465](https://zenodo.org/record/11942465)

Snakemake template A well documented Snakemake template that submits the Snakemake rules using the SLURM system.

See—<https://github.com/Luke-ebbis/snakemake-pixi/tree/main>

combifold-benchmark A Snakemake pipeline that downloads RCSB-PDB records and assesses how closely the predictions of these structures match the known crystals using the usalign algorithm. This pipeline imports parts of the pipeline I have build for assessment of protein structures, using the Snakemake module system.

See—<https://github.com/Luke-ebbis/combifold-benchmark/tree/v0.1.0>

complex-prediction A snakemake pipeline that runs the Combifold algorithm. Includes the configuration to work on the MPI-raven cluster.

See—<https://github.com/Luke-ebbis/complex-prediction/tree/v0.3.0>

B Statement on the use of AI

The ChatGPT model was used purely as a coding partner. It was used in cases to solve bugs in implementation. For instance, the submission of jobs via slurm (<https://chatgpt.com/share/00074ebb-92ee-45e2-bccf-82a3822bb38e>), asking for an error from a protein structure analysis library to be explained to me (<https://chatgpt.com/share/38352fb1-3fa1-4725-ba35-25778e9668a1>) or giving a reminder on matplotlib syntax (<https://chatgpt.com/share/7aa4236d-dff2-47e5-b1b0-5c21c767e6ff>).

For literature searches, the Web-Of-Science, and Google Scholar search engines were used. No AI systems were used for writing the report.

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